

CATEGORIES OF SPACE, TIME AND CHRONOTOPE IN THE PEACE OF ART AND LANGUAGE MEANS OF THEIR EXPRESSION

Karimova Nigora Maratovna

Lecturer at the Department of Russian Philology,

Fergana State University

Abstract. This article discusses the categories of "space", "time" and "chronotope" in a literary text and their main properties. The main language means of expressing these categories are also indicated.

Key words: artistic chronotopos, artistic time, artistic space, temporal and spatial determination of literary text.

Space and time are among the main semantic philosophical categories, without which the worldview model of reality is impossible. Ideas about space and time form a complex developing system, which is a reflection of diverse spatio-temporal relations. In philosophy, the categories of space and time take the form of an extremely generalized theoretical and ideological awareness by a socio-historical subject of space-time relations in their globality, integrity, inconsistency, in their correlation with a person, with his place and purpose in the world. Also, space and time, as forms of the existence of matter, are present in the real world in almost all its manifestations, and therefore, in the artistic reflection of this world, they turn out to be associated with a variety of linguistic forms and means of creating an artistic image. Fiction, in comparison with other types of art, handles real time and space as freely as possible. In a literary work, the space-time picture is always presented in a symbolic-ideological aspect. A literary text, regardless of what literary genre it belongs to, reflects events, phenomena, or the mental activity of a person in their spatio-temporal orientation. Literary scholars consider time and space as a reflection of the artist's philosophical ideas, analyze the specifics of artistic time and space in

different eras, in different literary trends and genres, study grammatical time in a work of art, consider time and space in their inseparable unity.

One of the universal components of the semantic structure of the text is artistic time. It reflects the correlation of events, associative, causal and psychological connections between them, creates a complex series of events that are built in the course of the plot development of the work. An artistic text differs from an everyday text in that the speaker constructs an imaginary world and produces an aesthetic effect on the reader. Time in fiction has certain properties associated with the specifics of the literary text, its features and the author's intention. Time in the text may have clearly defined or rather blurred boundaries (events, for example, may cover tens of years, a year, several days, a day, an hour, etc.), which may or may not be indicated in the work in relation to historical time or time that the author sets conditionally. Artistic time is systemic. This property of time is manifested in the organization of the aesthetic reality of the work, its inner world, and at the same time in a way associated with the embodiment of the author's concept, his perception of the surrounding reality, with the reflection of his own picture of the world. It is also necessary to distinguish between time as an immanent property of the work and the time of the flow of the text, which can be considered as the time of the reader; Thus, when considering a literary text, we are dealing with the antinomy “the time of the work is the time of the reader”. The time of the work itself can be non-uniform: as a result of temporal shifts, highlighting the central events, the depicted time can be compressed, reduced, and when comparing and describing simultaneous events, on the contrary, it can be stretched. Time in a work of art is transformed from irreversible into reversible, the time cursor acquires the ability to arbitrarily move through the artistic space within the author's space less often, reflecting the author's and character's perspective of the perception of the depicted world. The objectified cursor of existence turns into a subjective cursor of representation, or a cursor of aesthetic transformation (artistic cursor).

In a work of art, time can be multidimensional. This property of artistic time is connected with the very nature of a literary work, which, firstly, has an author and presupposes the presence of a reader, and secondly, boundaries: a beginning and an end. Thus, two temporal axes appear in the text - "the axes of narration" and "the axes of the events described". At the same time, the "narrative axis" is one-dimensional, while the "axis of events being described" is multidimensional. The correlation of these "axes" gives rise to the multidimensionality of artistic time and makes possible temporal shifts and multiplicity of temporal points of view in the structure of the text. In works of art, the real sequence of events is often violated, and temporal shifts, violation of the temporal sequence play an important role, which just affects the property of the multidimensionality of the work and can affect the author's division of the text into semantic segments or episodes. "Remaining essentially continuous in the successive change of temporal and spatial facts, the continuum in text reproduction is simultaneously broken up into separate episodes." The selection of these episodes is determined primarily by the aesthetic intentions of the author.

Artistic space, along with artistic time, is also one of the meaning-forming textual categories. The literary text is a certain spatial organization; thus, its analysis may include the consideration of its properties such as volume, configuration, system of repetitions and oppositions, as well as the analysis of such space properties as symmetries and connections. In a narrower sense, space in relation to a literary text is the spatial organization of its events, inextricably linked with the temporal organization of the work, and affecting the system of spatial images of the text. The elements of the text have a certain spatial configuration, and therefore there is a theoretical and practical possibility of spatial interpretation of the language tools used by the author, as well as the structure of the narrative. The space of a literary text, like time, has certain properties. Distinguish between broad and narrow understanding of space. This is due to the distinction between the external point of view on the text as a certain spatial organization, which is perceived by the reader,

and the internal point of view, which considers the spatial characteristics of the text itself as a relatively closed inner world that has self-sufficiency. These points of view on space complement each other, and when analyzing a literary text, it is necessary to take into account both of these aspects of space. The first aspect related to the external point of view on space is the “spatial architectonics” of the text, and the second aspect related to the spatial characteristics of the text is “artistic space”.

In a literary text, the space of the narrator and the space of characters are also distinguished. Their interaction makes the artistic space of the entire work multidimensional, voluminous and devoid of uniformity. But the space of the narrator is dominant, because it creates the integrity of the text and its internal unity and allows you to combine different angles of description and image. The space of the character can, in turn, be represented as expanding or contracting in relation to the character himself or to the particular object being described. The expansion of space can be motivated by the gradual expansion of the hero's experience, his knowledge of the outside world. The space actually seen by the character or the narrator can be supplemented by an imaginary space. The space given through the prism of the character's perception can be characterized by deformation associated with the reversibility of its elements and a special point of view on it. The space represented in the text may be specific, i.e. associated with local indicators, area names, etc., or, on the contrary, abstract, and have no local expression and connection with a specific location. The means of expressing spatial relations in the text and its spatial characteristics are mainly linguistic means: syntactic constructions with the meaning of location, existential sentences, prepositional-case forms with local meaning, verbs of motion, verbs with the meaning of finding a feature in space, adverbs of place, toponyms.

Each writer comprehends time and space in his own way, endowing them with their own characteristics, reflecting the worldview of the author. As a result, the artistic space created by the writer is unique and unlike any other artistic space and time. The connection of the content of the statement with space and time is already

set by the linguistic category of predicativity itself, which is the main characteristic of the sentence as a communicative linguistic unit. Since the phenomena of the surrounding world themselves exist in time and space, the linguistic form of their expression cannot but reflect this fundamental property of them. Using language, it is impossible to form an utterance without expressing the temporal correlation of its content with the moment of speech, without characterizing it as coinciding with it, preceding it, or able to follow it. Therefore, in every work, time and space are in unity. This unity of artistic time and artistic space is one of those structural and semantic categories of a literary text that link the elements and microstructures of a literary text into one integral, complex system. The categories of time and space are one of the means of unfolding the plot narrative.

The relationship of temporal and spatial relations, artistically mastered in literature, M.M. Bakhtin designated the chronotope (which literally means “time-space”). This term was first used in mathematical natural science and substantiated on the basis of Einstein's theory of relativity. M.M. Bakhtin used this term in literary criticism to express the inseparability of space and time (time as the fourth dimension of space). In literature, the chronotope has a significant genre significance. The genre and genre varieties of a work are determined precisely by the chronotope, and in literature the leading principle in the chronotope is time. Bakhtin believes that in the literary chronotope, time certainly dominates space, making it more meaningful and measurable. But, since the concept of chronotope is applicable not only in literature, but also in other areas of art, it is important to note that even in a literary chronotope, time may not always be the leading principle.

Yu.M. Lotman defines the artistic space in a literary work as "a continuum in which characters are placed and an action is performed", highlighting several of its subtypes: "magical and everyday, external or internal". At the same time, "the behavior of the characters is largely related to the space in which they are located and, moving from one space to another, a person is deformed according to its laws."

Having considered the content of the categories "space", "time" and "chronotope" in relation to literary works, we came to the conclusion that they, being integral components of being, are also immanent components of any literary text, and directly determine the organization and structure of the work, as well as affect the expression of the author's intent and the achievement of the desired aesthetic effect. Each of these categories has its own properties and characteristics, which allows the author to use these properties in his own way in the text (slow down or speed up the passage of time, expand the boundaries of space, etc.), reflecting his unique vision of the surrounding world in the work. The category of "chronotope" combines the categories of space and time and is the semantic center of the main events described by the author. Accordingly, for the objective linguistic expression of spatio-temporal characteristics in the text, there is a certain set of lexical and grammatical means by which the author fully creates a continuum of the work in front of the reader, determines the beginning, the course of events and the end. We have listed the most basic linguistic means, the analysis of which can allow one to penetrate into the essence of the work and highlight its chronotope.

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